

ISic0682

I.Sicily inscription 0682

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

marble

Object

plaque

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

2006.04

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Tyndaris

Place of origin (modern)

Tindari

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Tindari, Antiquarium di
Tindari

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 175748

EDCS 6100257

Bibliography

1888-. *L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 1989.0338i

Manganaro, G. 1989. Iscrizioni Latine nuove e vecchie della Sicilia. *Epigraphica*. 51: 161-196. At 164 no.13 fig.13

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